

This paper is published at Journal of International Journal of Metalcasting.

DOI: 10.1007/s40962-022-00878-7

[Erfan Heidari](#), Mohammadzadeh, M. Boutorabi, S. M. A. (2022)

Hot Rolling of Thin-Wall Ductile Cast Iron Produced by Ablation Casting

Abstract:

This study aims at investigating the possibility of rolling and increasing both the tensile strength and the elongation of thin-wall non-alloy ductile cast iron with a composition of C = 3%, Si = 4.15%, Mg = 0.04%, Mn = 0.36%, and carbon equivalent (CE) of 4.39% through the improvement of microstructure using ablation casting compared to conventional sand casting. A barium containing post-inoculant (Si = 72–77%, Ba = 2.0–3.0%, Ca = 1.0–2.0%, Al = 0.8–1.5%, Fe = bal.) was employed as inoculant to produce thin-wall ductile cast iron castings. Specimens with initial thicknesses of 4.4 and 8.3 mm were hot rolled at 780 °C and 900 °C for ablation and conventional method, respectively. The rolling process on the specimens improved the mechanical properties significantly. The microstructure of the ablation specimens after rolling consisted of elongated graphite, ferrite encapsulating graphite, bainite and martensite, while the microstructure of the normal specimen after rolling consisted of elongated graphite, carbide, and martensite. The ablation specimens with thicknesses of 4.4 and 8.3 mm were subjected to strains of 58% and 78%, respectively, and the ultimate tensile strength values obtained were 1257 and 873 MPa, respectively. Conventional specimens were also subjected to strains of 34% and 58%, and the ultimate tensile strength values obtained were 948 and 745 MPa, respectively. Moreover, the highest elongation (16.3%) was reported for the 8.3-mm-thick specimen. The results show that rolling on thin-wall ductile cast iron castings improved the microstructure and increased the tensile properties of cast iron components.

Keywords: thin-wall ductile cast iron, hot rolling, microstructure, tensile properties, ablation

[Erfan Heidari](#) Contact Info:

☎ +98 9121237533

✉ erfan.heidari@mst.edu

[Erfan Heidari](#) Available at :

Google scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=cs7MW3gAAAAJ&hl=en>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8619-6347>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Erfan-Heidari-4>

Web of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/JCN-7367-2023>

ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/deposit?page=1&size=20>

Bepress : <https://works.bepress.com/erfan-heidari/>

Figshare: https://figshare.com/authors/Erfan_Heidari/17028147

Linkdin: <http://www.linkedin.com/in/erfanheidari>

SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=6178326